

Comparative Study on Cognitive Functions between Early Onset Vs Late Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

A cross-sectional analysis of neurocognitive performance across age groups

Vidhya A¹, Sivaraman S², Ronald Roy K³

¹Junior Resident, ²HOD and Professor, ³Associate Professor
Psychiatry, Trichy SRM Medical college hospital Research Centre, Tiruchirappalli, India

Abstract

Background: Alcohol consumption disorder is characterized by a problematic pattern of compulsive and uncontrolled alcohol use that is linked with clinically substantial impairment or distress. Researchers have found that those who suffer from alcoholism are more likely to have cognitive problems, and that early-onset alcoholism is more severe than late-onset alcoholism. However, they have not assessed the extent of cognitive impairment in early onset and late onset alcoholism, nor have they compared the cognitive processes that are associated with each of these stages of alcoholism. To contribute to this understanding, the present study is designed to assess and compare cognitive functions and one of the domains related to executive functions that is cognitive flexibility.

Methodology: This is a type of cross-sectional study on 140 participants (70 early onset alcohol dependence and 70 late onset alcohol dependence) from psychiatric OPD treatment-seeking patients. Nonprobability sampling (convenient sampling) was used. Males with Age range: 18 to 50 years, Age of onset of alcohol dependence, EARLY ONSET - 18 to 25 years, LATE ONSET - >25 years, Education: 8th standard and above, Right handedness, Alcohol dependence according to ICD-10 criteria (WHO, 1992) were included. Psychoactive substance use disorders other than alcohol dependence and nicotine dependence, diagnosed primary psychiatric disorders, medical conditions that contribute to cognitive impairment, and patients with intellectual disability were excluded. Determination of the level of cognitive function was made by Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination (ACE-III). Determination of cognitive flexibility using Trail Making A and B neuropsychological tests was done.

Results: Correlation of memory for early onset alcohol dependence p-value is 0.034, and late onset alcohol dependence is 0.018. Correlation of fluency in early onset alcohol dependence patients p-value is 0.041, and late onset alcohol dependence patients p-value is 0.024. Correlation of language in early onset alcohol dependence patients is 0.026, and late onset alcohol patients is 0.022. Correlation of visuospatial ability in early onset p-value is 0.031, and late onset is 0.020. Correlation of early onset ACE-III p-value is 0.027, and late onset is 0.014. Correlation of TMA in early onset p-value is 0.023, and late onset p-value is 0.019. Correlation of early onset TMB p-value is 0.017, and late onset p-value is 0.011.

Conclusion: The cognitive impairment was statistically more seen in early onset alcohol dependence patients (<25 years) with respect to memory, fluency, language, visuospatial ability, ACE-III, and TMA. TMB was statistically more seen in early onset alcohol dependence patients.

Keywords: Alcohol dependence, Cognitive impairment, Early onset, Late onset, Neuropsychological

INTRODUCTION

Alcohol consumption disorder is characterized by a problematic pattern of compulsive and uncontrolled alcohol use that is linked with clinically substantial impairment or distress. Patients who have had ongoing issues with alcohol have a three- to fourfold greater risk of dying prematurely. The manifestations of

alcoholism are widely different; nonetheless, some typical characterizations include being unable to control one's drinking, continuing to drink despite being aware of the repercussions, and ignoring one's duties [1]. Cravings, obsessions, and compulsions about alcohol consumption, tolerance, blackouts, withdrawal, and the repercussions of disease are common signs of alcoholism (e.g., health, relationship, legal, financial, employment, educational). Early onset alcoholism is characterized by the development of an addiction to alcohol before the age of 25. Late onset alcoholism, on the other hand, is characterized by the development of an addiction to alcohol beyond the age of 25 (onset of alcohol dependence after the age of 25 years). There are a myriad of difficulties that can arise as a result of alcohol use disorder, some of which include the possibility for major health problems, social problems, complications connected to withdrawal, and even mortality at an earlier age. Researchers have found that those who suffer from alcoholism are more likely to have cognitive problems, and that early-onset alcoholism is more severe than late-onset alcoholism. These findings come from a number of different studies [2].

Cognition is what enables humans to function in everyday life: personal, social, and occupational. The ability to attend to things in a selective and focused way, to concentrate over a period of time, to learn new information and skills, to plan, determine strategies for actions, and execute them, to comprehend language and use verbal skills for communication and self-expression, to retain information and manipulate it to solve complex problems are examples of mental processes that are referred to as cognitive functions. Cognitive deficits may result in the inability to:

1. Pay attention.
2. Quickly process information.
3. Remember and retrieve information.
4. Quickly respond to information.
5. Exercise critical thinking to plan, organize, and find solutions to problems.
6. Start the conversation off.

Cognitive Domains

Active rehearsal, the processing of information, and the manipulation of data are all involved in working memory. It would appear that working memory is dependent on the activity of the prefrontal cortex [3]. The term "executive function" (EF) refers to the capacity to use abstract concepts, to formulate an appropriate problem-solving test for the attainment of future goals, to plan one's actions, to work out strategies for problem-solving, and to execute these with the self-monitoring of one's mental and physical processes. Attention and information processing is the ability to identify relevant stimuli, focus on those stimuli rather than others (also known as selective attention), the ability to perform a task while being exposed to distracting stimuli (focused attention), and the ability to maintain focus on the stimulus until it is processed (also known as sustained attention or vigilance) [4].

Alcohol Dependence and Cognitive Deficits

Consuming an excessive amount of alcohol despite the fact that it negatively impacts an individual's physical, mental, interpersonal, and social well-being is a defining characteristic of alcohol use disorders. These effects are mediated by the brain, which undergoes changes in its structure, function, and fundamental physiology as a result of these effects [5]. The functioning of the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex has been linked to impaired performance on tests of working memory and cognitive flexibility in alcoholics and other people who regularly consume alcohol. It was found that the age at which heavy drinking began was a significantly better predictor of these alcoholic patterns than the length of time that heavy drinking was engaged in. According to these findings, the hypothesis that consistent and excessive alcohol consumption at a young age may have more detrimental effects on the future social, interpersonal, cognitive, and physical functioning of an alcoholic than the length of time that an alcoholic consumes excessive amounts of alcohol warrants further investigation. Subjects who began experiencing alcohol dependence at a younger age (less than 25 years old) reported higher lifetime rates of specific phobia, antisocial behaviors, and virtually all addictive disorders. Before one reaches the age of 25, medical professionals consider this to be the beginning of early-onset alcohol dependence [6].

However, they have not assessed the extent of cognitive impairment in early onset and late onset alcoholism, nor have they compared the cognitive processes that are associated with each of these stages of

alcoholism. Although a number of researchers have found that alcoholics have poor executive function, very few in-depth investigations that use executive function assessments have been carried out on alcoholics. Patients who experience alcohol dependency at an earlier stage are likely to have more severe impairments in their cognitive functioning than patients who experience alcohol dependence at a later stage. To contribute to this understanding, the present study is designed to assess and compare cognitive functions and one of the domains related to executive functions, which is cognitive flexibility.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design: Observational

Type of Study: Cross-sectional

Study Duration: 2 years

Ethical Consideration: This study was approved by the Institute Ethical Committee, and data collection was done after obtaining informed consent.

Study Population:

- **Total Sample Size:** 140
 - Early onset alcohol dependence: 70
 - Late onset alcohol dependence: 70
- **Recruitment Process:** Non-probability (convenient sampling)

Inclusion Criteria:

- **A.** Male, with age range: 18 to 50 years
- **B.** Age of onset of alcohol dependence:
 - Early onset: 18 to 25 years
 - Late onset: >25 years
- **C.** Education: 8th standard and above
- **D.** Right-handedness
- **E.** Alcohol dependence according to ICD-10 criteria (WHO, 1992)

Exclusion Criteria:

- **A.** Psychoactive substance use disorders other than alcohol dependence and nicotine dependence
- **B.** Diagnosed primary psychiatric disorders
- **C.** Medical conditions that contribute to cognitive impairment
- **D.** Patients with intellectual disability

After obtaining informed consent, selection of patients according to inclusion and exclusion criteria was done. Data was recorded in a preformed and pretested semi-structured proforma for sociodemographic profile and substance use.

Assessment Tools:

- **Cognitive Function Assessment:** Addenbrooke's Cognitive Examination (ACE-III)
- **Cognitive Flexibility Assessment:** Trail Making A and B neuropsychological tests

Statistical Analysis:

For continuous variables, descriptive statistics were reported as mean \pm SD, and for categorical variables, frequencies and percentages were reported. Statistical significance was determined using the Chi-square test at the 5% level. If the expected cell count was less than 5, Fischer's exact test was applied. An independent t-test was used to compare the cognitive deficits between early onset and late onset alcohol dependence patients.

IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows, Version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Chicago, IL), was used to statistically analyze the data.

RESULTS

Cognitive functions in EARLY ONSET ALCOHOL DEPENDENCE PATIENTS

Figure 1: Memory Scores in Early Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 35.7% had a memory of 20, 11.4% with memory of 12, 21.4% with memory of 23, 5.7% 19, 8.6% 13, 2.9% 16,17,18 respectively (Figure 1).

Figure 2: Fluency Scores in Early Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 27.1% with fluency of 8, 22.9% with fluency of 10, 21.4% with fluency of 7 and 9 respectively, 2.9% with fluency of 11 and 12 (Figure 2).

Figure 3: Language Scores in Early Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 70% had language of 16, 21.4% with language value of 18 and 4.3% with language of 14 and 19 respectively (Figure 3).

Figure 4: Visuospatial Ability (VSA) Scores in Early Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 27.1% were with VSA of 8, 22.9% with VSA of 10, 21.4% with VSA of 7 and 9 respectively, 2.9% with VSA of 11 and 12 (Figure 4).

Figure 5: ACE-III Scores in Early Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 30% had ACE-III of 65, 20% with 23, 14.3% 68, 12.9% with 69, 5.7% 20, 5.7% with 67 and 20 respectively (Figure 5).

Figure 6: TMA Scores in Early Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 24.3% had TMA of 78 sec, 25.7% with TMA of 75 sec, 20% with TMA of 83 sec, 7.1% with TMA of 76 and 77 sec respectively, 5.7% with TMA of 80 sec and 2.9% with 79 sec, 81 and 82 sec respectively (Figure 6).

Figure 7: TMB Scores in Early Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 21.4% had TMB 160 sec, 18.6% with TMB of 230 sec, 10% with TMB of 190 sec. Remaining 2.9% were with TMB of 235, 215, 205, 200, 195 and 150 sec respectively. Around 1.4% had TMB of 225, 220, 165 and 155 sec respectively (Figure 7).

Cognitive functions in late ONSET ALCOHOL DEPENDENCE PATIENTS

Figure 8: Memory Scores in Late Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

There were about 54.3% with memory of 22, 34.2% with memory of 23, 5.7% with a memory of 24 and 2.9% with memory of 20 and 21 respectively (Figure 8).

Figure 9: Fluency Scores in Late Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

There are about 48.6% with fluency of 12, 28.6% with fluency of 11, 18.6% with a fluency of 13, 2.9% with fluency of 10 and 1.4% with a fluency of 14 (Figure 9).

Figure 10: VSA Scores in Late Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 54.3% had VSA of 10, 37.1% with VSA of 9, 5.7% with VSA of 8 and 2.9% with VSA of 11 (Figure 10).

Figure 11: Language Scores in Late Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Majority of the participants 35.7% had language value of 20, 21.4% with language of 23, 11.4% with language of 12, 8.6% with a language of 13, 5.7% with language of 19, 2.9% with language of 16,17 and 18 respectively; and, 1.4% with language of 14,15 and 24 respectively (Figure 11).

Figure 12: ACE-III Scores in Late Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 20% with ACE-III with 78 and 80, 17.1% with value of 76, 11.4% 81, 5.7% 75, 4.3% 82, 7.1% 77 and 1.4% 74 (Figure 12).

Figure 13: TMA Scores in Late Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 21.4% with TMA of 26 sec, 18.6% 28 and 24 sec respectively, 7.1% with TMA of 25, 29 and 30 sec respectively; and, 1.4% 34,36,38,39 and 23 sec respectively (Figure 13).

Figure 14: TMB Scores in Late Onset Alcohol Dependence Patients

Around 18.6% with TMB value of 75 sec, 21.4% with value of 58 sec, 10% with a value of 66 sec, 8.6% with a value of 62 sec, 2.9% with a value of 76, 69, 67, 68 and 56 sec respectively (Figure 14).

Table 1: Association of variables using Pearson chi-square between early and late onset alcoholism.

The cognitive impairment was statistically more seen in early onset alcohol dependence patients (<25 years) with respect to memory, fluency, language, VSA, ACE-III, TMA. TMB was statistically more seen in early onset alcohol dependence patients.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to compare the levels of cognitive impairment seen in patients with early onset alcohol dependency to those seen in patients with late onset alcohol dependence. In order to accomplish this, we recruited 70 patients suffering from early-onset alcoholism and 70 patients suffering from late-onset alcohol dependence. According to the findings, people who struggle with alcoholism exhibit cognitive deficits in a number of different areas, such as focused attention and information processing, mental flexibility, working memory in both modality (i.e., auditory and visuospatial), learning and memory, recognition ability, and visual memory. These findings are in agreement with the findings of a number of other studies that have shown abnormalities in sustained and divided attention, phonemic fluency, visual working memory, learning and memory, and visuospatial & visual memory deficiencies [7]. Several studies have shown that alcoholics experience abnormalities on neuropsychological tests that are related to executive function deficits.

However, not every alcoholic exhibits the cognitive problems associated with alcoholism. Cognitive impairments could be caused by a combination of personal and lifestyle factors, as well as those associated with alcohol consumption and dependency. The age of onset, the age of dependence, the number of years of alcohol use and dependence, relapses, and other co-morbid disorders are important factors related to cognitive deficits in alcoholics. Individualistic factors, such as age and education, health status, and pre-morbid functioning, are also important factors. Both age and level of schooling have been shown to influence cognitive abilities. Because of the changes in the brain that come with getting older, drinking alcohol may have an even more negative effect on a person's cognitive abilities if they are an older adult. On the other side, research has shown that beginning to drink alcohol at a younger age is an excellent indicator of developing alcohol-related issues later in life [8].

A number of studies have found a connection between cognitive impairments and parameters that are associated with the consumption of alcohol and alcohol dependence, showing that persons who had a longer length of dependence and frequent hospital readmissions had a greater number of cognitive abnormalities in comparison to individuals who had a shorter period of dependence and fewer readmissions [9].

Smeraldi and Movalli have found that alcoholism produces varying degrees of cognitive abnormalities in its victims. According to their findings, 45.7% of people with alcoholism indicated a general deterioration in their cognitive skills. While 26.1% showed deficits in verbal memory, 32.6% demonstrated deficits in working memory, 50.0% demonstrated deficits in psychomotor speed and coordination, 30.4% demonstrated deficits in verbal fluency, 58.7% demonstrated deficits in selective attention, 13.0% demonstrated deficits in planning, 41.3% demonstrated deficits in executive functions, and 56.5% demonstrated deficits in sustained attention. Variability in cognitive impairments has also been found by a number of other researchers in patients with alcoholism [10]. Ihara and Berrios studied cognitive functions in adults with alcoholism and observed that certain cognitive functions were intact in individuals with alcoholism, while some other cognitive functions revealed abnormalities [11].

Cognitive impairments are associated with poor prognosis outcomes and can have a negative influence. Generally speaking, pharmaceutical treatments, behavioral treatments, and motivational interviews are the most popular therapy modalities utilized in the treatment of patients who suffer from alcoholism [12]. The majority of treatments for alcoholism do not take into account the negative impact that cognitive deficiencies can have on recovery. Cognitive remediation has been demonstrated to be beneficial in reducing cognitive deficiencies in a variety of clinical diseases, according to intervention studies that utilized this treatment [13]. As a result, future research should investigate the usefulness of cognitive remediation in conjunction with other treatment modalities for the purpose of improving treatment efficacy in the context of treating persons who have early onset alcoholism.

According to the findings of the study, late-onset alcohol misuse is typically caused by traumatic antecedents or events, and the study also found that older people frequently misuse alcohol as a means of coping with the difficulties associated with aging and living [14]. According to the findings of the study, having an understanding of the underlying causes of alcohol abuse can help provide essential information for selecting an appropriate intervention in the process of rehabilitating an alcohol-dependent individual to obtaining abstinence or achieving sobriety.

Some studies also informed how the involvement of family and the social network of an alcohol-dependent person in the treatment process can be essential to understanding the behavior of an alcohol-abusive person and establishing the etiology of alcohol misuse. This vital information also helps to inform an effective intervention approach, which can be utilized to aid an alcoholic in reaching sobriety and abstinence from alcohol consumption.

Despite this fact, need-based treatment was not developed specifically for the treatment of substance misuse. According to the findings of this study, it is commendable to employ the approach or its principles in the treatment of substance misuse if one wants to get the desired results. The abusive person's ideas and thoughts are beneficially integrated into the therapy process through therapeutic engagement, which contributes to the achievement of desired outcomes. According to the social cognitive theory given by Bandura, the participation of individuals who are experiencing distress in treatment procedures has been shown to promote self-esteem, which in turn improves self-efficacy, which is essential to the process of behavioral change.

Additionally, the motivation that is obtained from family members and the support that is obtained from one's social network during treatment processes helps to improve one's self-efficacy for behavioral change and assists an individual in achieving desired results in a therapeutic environment and in the community [15].

LIMITATIONS

1. It was a cross-sectional study, no follow-up study was made.
2. The systemic and mental illnesses were ruled out with basic investigations in addition to clinical findings. Imaging was not attempted to rule out structural defects.
3. The main limiting factor is tobacco use, which is heavy in alcohol dependence patients; it affects cognitive functions similar to alcohol, but this factor cannot be eliminated in the present study.

4. Quantity of alcohol was not considered.

CONCLUSION

Alcoholism has the potential to cause a wide variety of cognitive problems. These deficiencies could be caused by a combination of several individual characteristics as well as those related to alcohol consumption and alcohol dependence. In the current investigation, cognitive impairments were shown to be more severe in patients with early-onset alcohol dependency than in patients with late-onset alcohol dependence. The tasks associated with other executive functions, such as decision-making, planning, and set-shifting, should also be included in any future research on this topic. According to the findings of this study, treatment for alcoholism should include a cognitive rehabilitation program to improve treatment efficacy by reducing cognitive deficiencies caused by alcoholism.

FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The study on the comparison of early vs late onset alcohol dependence patients and their cognitive dysfunctions is limited. Hence, in the future, more studies are required to help with cognitive remediation and rehabilitation. Future studies should consider the duration of alcohol dependence, the quantity of alcohol consumed, and its influence on cognitive functions.

REFERENCES

- [1] M.A. Schuckit, "Alcohol-use disorders," *Lancet*, vol. 373, no. 9662, pp. 492–501, 2009.
- [2] D.E. Jonas, "Screening and counseling for unhealthy alcohol use in primary care settings," *Med Clin North Am.*, vol. 101, no. 4, pp. 823–837, 2017.
- [3] S. Funahashi, "Prefrontal Cortex and Working Memory," in *Dorsolateral Prefrontal Cortex*. Brain Science. Springer, Singapore, 2022. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-19-7268-3_10
- [4] J.K. Trivedi, "Cognitive deficits in psychiatric disorders: Current status," *Indian J Psychiatry*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 10–20, Jan. 2006, doi: 10.4103/0019-5545.31613.
- [5] M.J. Rosenbloom, A. Pfefferbaum, and E.V. Sullivan, "Structural Brain Alterations Associated With Alcoholism," *Alcohol Health Res World*, vol. 19, no. 4, pp. 266–272, 1995.
- [6] R. Kumar, K.J. Kumar, V. Benegal, and B.N. Roopesh, "Cognitive deficits in early onset alcoholism," Dec. 2016.
- [7] L.K. Dawson and I. Grant, "Alcoholics' initial organizational and problem-solving skills predict learning and memory performance on the Rey–Osterrieth Complex Figure," *Journal of the International Neuropsychological Society*, vol. 6, no. 01, pp. 12–19, 2000.
- [8] M.A. Schottenbauer, D. Hommer, and H. Weingartner, "Memory Deficits Among Alcoholics: Performance on a Selective Reminding Task," *Aging, Neuropsychology, and Cognition*, vol. 14, no. 5, pp. 505–516, 2007.
- [9] M.A. Al-Zahrani and Y.A. Elsayed, "The impacts of substance abuse and dependence on neuropsychological functions in a sample of patients from Saudi Arabia," *Behavioral and Brain Functions*, vol. 5, no. 1, pp. 1–11, 2009.
- [10] C. Smeraldi, M. Movalli, M. Cavicchioli, S.M. Angelone, and C. Maffei, "Cognitive deficits related to alcohol abuse: a preliminary study," *European Psychiatry*, vol. 28, 2013.
- [11] H. Ihara and G.E. Berrios, "Group and case study of the dysexecutive syndrome in alcoholism without amnesia," *Journal of Neurology, Neurosurgery, and Psychiatry*, vol. 68, no. 6, pp. 731–737, 2000.
- [12] K.D. Cicerone, D.M. Langenbahn, C. Braden, J.F. Malec, K. Kalmar, M. Fraas, et al., "Evidence-based cognitive rehabilitation: updated review of the literature from 2003 through 2008," *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, vol. 92, no. 4, pp. 519–530, 2011.
- [13] M.S. Keshavan, S. Vinogradov, J. Rumsey, J. Sherrill, and A. Wagner, "Cognitive training in mental disorders: update and future directions," *Am J Psychiatry*, vol. 171, no. 5, pp. 510–522, 2014.
- [14] K. Graham, D. Clarke, C. Bois, V. Carver, L. Dolinki, C. Smythe, S. Harrison, J. Marshman, and P. Brett, "Addictive behavior of older adults," *Addictive Behaviors*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 331–348, May 1996.
- [15] F. Pajares, A. Prestin, J. Chen, and R.L. Nabi, "Social cognitive theory and media effects," *The SAGE handbook of media processes and effects*, Sep. 11, 2009, pp. 283–297.